

ACADEMIA | Letters

A Study on the Beliefs and Attitudes of Selected College Students on the Existence of Extraterrestrial Intelligent Life

Frederick Edward Fabella

This year, the U.S. government released a report on its review of unidentified aerial phenomena (UAP) observed by military aviators between 2004 and 2018. There have been a total of 144 UAPs that have been reported during this period.[1] UAP is the new terminology that is now being used to refer to unidentified flying objects or UFOs.[2]

The interest in UFOs was sparked in 1947, when a rancher in New Mexico came upon unusual debris. The local sheriff then informed the Roswell Army Airfield about this discovery. Interestingly enough, the military issued a press release claiming that a “flying disc” had been recovered. On July 8th of that year, a local newspaper published a story with the headline “RAAF Captures Flying Saucer On Ranch in Roswell Region.” Shortly thereafter, the military announced that it was in fact a weather balloon.[3]

One location that has been associated with UFOs is Area 51, a patch of desert in Nevada[4] Area 51 is where the U2 spy plane was built and is where espionage programs are devised.[5] It became associated with UFOs when physicist Bob Lazar made a public TV appearance in 1989 claiming that he had been hired to reverse-engineer spacecraft that was being kept there.[6] The secretive nature of Area 51 has since fueled speculations that Lazar’s assertions may be true.

In 1984, NASA’s Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence or SETI was established,[7] which can be considered as an official acknowledgment that alien life could exist. In fact, as of this year, NASA has been able to identify and confirm 4,461 exoplanets of which 165 have been classified as terrestrial or possibly similar to Earth.[8]

Even the Vatican Observatory has an astronomical telescope in Arizona. And its chief

astronomer has stated that they are open to the possibility of life on other planets.[9]

In view of the foregoing, this study was conducted to ascertain the attitudes towards and beliefs about extraterrestrial intelligent life. This research was done in the Philippines, and college students from the province of Rizal (San Mateo and Rodriguez), Marikina City and Quezon City were invited to voluntarily take part in this quantitative study during a week in September of 2021. There were 70 respondents, 51 females and 19 males, whose ages ranged between 16 to 28. This study utilized a 20-item researcher-made instrument using a 4-point Likert scale. The weighted means were computed for each item and the corresponding verbal interpretations are indicated.

The findings are displayed in the following tables.

Computed Weighted Means of the Responses		
Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I watch films / movies / TV series about UFOs / aliens	2.8428571	Sometimes
2. I read books / e-books about UFOs / aliens	2.2571429	Rarely
3. I watch / read / listen to news about UFOs / aliens	2.5857143	Sometimes
4. I read websites and blogs about UFOs / aliens	2.4857143	Rarely
5. I would describe my religious beliefs as	2.8142857	Strong
6. Extraterrestrial intelligent life other than human beings exist.	3.00	Agree
7. There are people who have actually witnessed UFOs.	2.8142857	Agree
8. There are people who have witnessed extraterrestrial intelligent beings on Earth.	2.7857143	Agree
9. There are people who have come into contact and communicated with extraterrestrial intelligent beings.	2.4714286	Disagree
10. There are people who have been abducted by extraterrestrial intelligent beings.	2.3428571	Disagree
11. People who claim they have witnessed UFOs may have been seeing a natural and explainable phenomenon or man-made object.	2.7142857	Agree
12. People who claim they have witnessed extraterrestrial intelligent beings on Earth were only experiencing some form of delusion, hysteria or hallucination.	2.5142857	Disagree

13. People who claim they came into contact and communicated with or were abducted by extraterrestrial intelligent beings are only making up a story to gain attention.	2.5	Disagree
14. The claim that extraterrestrial intelligent beings exist or have visited Earth is just part of conspiracy theories	2.6428571	Agree
15. If extraterrestrial intelligent beings did exist, I believe they are only neutral observers.	2.8857143	Agree
16. If extraterrestrial intelligent beings did exist, I believe they want to help us.	2.6	Agree
17. If extraterrestrial intelligent beings did exist, I believe they want to harm us.	2.2428571	Disagree
18. The governments concerned should disclose whatever they know about UFOs, whether they exist or not	2.5571429	Agree
19. Knowing the truth about UFOs can disrupt public order and political and economic stability of the world	2.7285714	Agree
20. The existence of extraterrestrial intelligent beings is contradictory to my religious beliefs	2.3142857	Disagree

Scale for Items 1-4	
Verbal Interpretation	Score
Never	1.00 – 1.75
Rarely	1.76 – 2.50
Sometimes	2.56 – 3.25
Often	3.26 – 4.00

Scale for Item 5	
Verbal Interpretation	Score
Not very strong	1.00 – 1.75
Somewhat strong	1.76 – 2.50
Strong	2.56 – 3.25
Very strong	3.26 – 4.00

Scale for Items 6-20	
Verbal Interpretation	Score
Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.75
Disagree	1.76 – 2.50
Agree	2.56 – 3.25
Strongly Agree	3.26 – 4.00

Correlation between Level of Strength of Religious Beliefs and Belief in Existence of Extraterrestrial Intelligent Life	
Using Pearson r	
R: -0.3374.	Low inverse relationship

Correlation between Age and Belief in Existence of Extraterrestrial Intelligent Life	
Using Pearson r	
R: -0.1526	Low inverse relationship

Difference of Male and Female Belief in the Existence of Extraterrestrial Intelligent Life	
Using Welch t-test	
Two-tailed P value: 0.6398	Not statistically significant

Exposure to information fictional or otherwise about UFOs was measured by items 1-4. And it could be seen that films / movies / TV series about UFOs / aliens and news about UFOs / aliens are the primary source of such. But such exposure occurred only *sometimes*.

While the respondents' religious beliefs are *strong*, they also *agree* that extraterrestrial intelligent life exists.

The respondents *agree* that there are people who have actually witnessed UFOs and have witnessed extraterrestrial intelligent beings on earth.

The respondents also *agree* that people who claim they have witnessed UFOs may have been seeing a natural and explainable phenomenon or man-made object. Furthermore, they also *agree* that information concerning the possible existence of UFOs may just be product of conspiracy theories.

In addition, the respondents *agree* that if extraterrestrial beings did exist, they are neutral observers and are here to help us. Ironically, although the respondents *agree* that governments concerned should disclose whatever they know about UFOs, whether they exist or not, they also *agree* that knowing the truth about UFOs can disrupt public order and political and economic stability of the world.

The respondents also *agree* that the existence of extraterrestrial intelligent life does not contradict their religious beliefs.

A Glocalities study, conducted among 26,492 people from 24 countries stated that 61% of those surveyed believe that life exists on other planets and that 47% believe further that intelligent alien civilizations are out there.[10] This appears to be consistent with this study's findings based on Item 6.

Although some astrophysicists fear that whatever alien intelligence humans come into contact with may not have the Earth's best interests in mind,[11] the respondents do not agree with this as indicated in Item 17. However, in 2007, an obscure U.S. government program called the Advanced Aerospace Threat Identification Program (AATIP) was established to investigate UAPs. In a 2021 interview, it's former director, Elizondo reports that these UAPs have been observed in the vicinity of nuclear facilities. He further claims that these UAPs have been able to shut down the country's nuclear capabilities.[12]

If there has been an attempt by the powers-that-be to keep secret the existence of an alien presence, one reason could be that extraterrestrial technology poses an existential threat to the global power structure,[13] which appears to be consistent with the findings in item 19.

A low inverse correlation was found between strength of the respondents' religious beliefs and their belief in the existence of extraterrestrial intelligent life. There also appears to be a low inverse correlation between the respondents' age and their belief in the existence of extraterrestrial intelligent life. In comparing male and female respondents' responses concerning their belief in the existence of extraterrestrial intelligent life, no significant difference was found.

The researcher recommends further investigation concerning these attitudes and beliefs as this study is limited by the number of respondents. As news about these phenomena are now being released, it is only fitting that further studies should be done in this area to ascertain the public's potential reaction to the truth coming out.

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